

Isoquinoline Derivatives. Part IX

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Treatment of the oxime of 1-phenyl-3-phenoxypropan-2-one with sodium and ethanol affords 1-phenyl-2-aminopropane. 1-Phenyl-3-phenoxyethyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline and the corresponding 3-hydroxyethyl derivative, 3-piperidinocarbonyl-, 3-piperidinomethyl-, 3-benzyl-3,4-dihydro-, 3-benzyl-, and 3-(α -1-piperidylbenzyl)-isoquinolines have been synthesised.

One of the major drawbacks of papaverine and related synthetic isoquinoline antispasmodics is their weakly basic character. The salts are easily hydrolysed producing acidic reaction, which causes pain at the site of injection. To obviate this difficulty it has been considered desirable to introduce further basic groups in the isoquinoline ring with substituents which may be expected to promote activity. In fact, the introduction of a 3-pyridyl group in 1-position of 3-methyl-6,7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline has furnished a compound much more active than papaverine (Merck, G.P., 613,005/1935).

Based on the observation that 3-methylisoquinolines are potent antispasmodics with low toxicity (Kreitmair, *Arch. Exp. Path. Pharm.*, 1932, 164, 509; Sugawara and Sugimoto, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1941, 61, 62) and that replacement of the benzyl group in 1-position of papaverine type of compounds by phenyl increases activity, it has been considered desirable to introduce basically substituted methyl group in 3-position of 1-phenylisoquinoline derivatives. As an approach to the problem, the reduction of the oxime of 1-phenyl-3-phenoxypropan-2-one (Pfeiffer and Epler, *Annalen*, 1940, 545, 263) has been attempted with sodium and ethanol, when 1-phenyl-2-aminopropane has been obtained, obviously through the reductive fission of the aromatic ether group. Similar observations on the fission of aromatic ethers by the action of sodium in refluxing pyridine have been recorded (Prey, *Ber.*, 1943, 76B, 156). 1-Phenyl-3-phenoxy-2-aminopropane (I) has been prepared by hydrolysis of the Leuckart reaction product from 1-phenyl-3-phenoxypropan-2-one. The benzoyl derivative of (I), when subjected to the Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation, has afforded 1-phenyl-3-phenoxyethyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline (II), which after dehydrogenation has been treated with hydrobromic acid to yield the 3-hydroxyethyl derivative (III). The low yields of the products in these stages, specially in the Leuckart reaction, stood in the way of further progress.

As a further approach to the problem, ethyl isoquinoline-3-carboxylate (Clemo and Hoggarth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 95) has been condensed with piperidine to afford 3-piperidinocarbonyl-isoquinoline (IV), which on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride has yielded 3-piperidino-methylisoquinoline (V).

Papaverine carries a substituted benzyl group at 1-position of the isoquinoline. 3-Benzyl-isoquinoline has been synthesised to ascertain the effect of a benzyl group at 3-position instead

of at 1-position. This compound has been described by Rügheimer (*Annalen*, 1903, **326**, 261; 1903, **328**, 326). He obtained it along with the 4-isomer by treatment of benzoyltetrahydroisoquinoline with benzaldehyde under pressure at 200° and subsequent separation of the isomers. 3-Benzylisoquinoline has now been prepared by an unambiguous method: *N*-Formyl- α -benzyl- β -phenylethylamine (Rajagopalan, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, **14A**, 126; Dey and Ramanathan *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1943, **9**, 193) has been subjected to the Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation with a mixture of polyphosphoric acid and phosphorus oxychloride to afford 3-benzyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline (VI), which on dehydrogenation with Pd-C has yielded 3-benzylisoquinoline (VII), the physical characteristics of which have been found to be at variance with those described by Rügheimer (*loc. cit.*). The compound (VII) has been brominated and the bromo-derivative treated with piperidine to yield (VIII).

The biological activity of the compounds is under study.

EXPERIMENTAL

Oxime of 1-phenyl-3-phenoxypropane-2-one was prepared by the interaction of 1-phenyl-3-phenoxypropane-2-one (Pfeiffer and Epler, *loc. cit.*) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of NaOH. It was recrystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 94-96°. (Found: N, 5.74. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 5.81%).

Formation of 1-Phenyl-2-aminopropane.—Sodium (20 g.) was gradually added to a solution of the preceding oxime (15 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (220 c.c.) and the mixture refluxed till complete dissolution of sodium. It was poured in ice-water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was shaken with HCl (dil.) and the acid solution basified with NaOH. The liberated amine was taken up in ether and dried (K_2CO_3). After removal of the ether, a viscous oil (6 g.) was obtained, which was benzoylated by the Schotten-Baumann method, and the product was recrystallised from dilute ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 132-33°. (Found: N, 5.79. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{17}ON$: N, 5.86%).

The above benzoyl derivative was identified with an authentic sample (British Pharmacopœia, 1958, p. 43).

1-Phenyl-3-phenoxy-2-aminopropane (I).—Formic Acid (98%, 46 g.) was neutralised with ammonium carbonate (46 g.) and the solution was distilled up to 165°. The residue was treated with 1-phenyl-3-phenoxypropane-2-one (30 g.). The mixture after refluxing at 180-90° for 16 hours was hydrolysed by HCl (conc., 100 c.c.) under reflux for 6 hours. The solution was washed with ether, cooled, and basified. The liberated amine was taken up in ether and the extract dried (K_2CO_3). Removal of the ether left the amine as a thick liquid (2 g.), which was characterised as the benzoyl derivative, crystallising from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 124-25°. (Found: N, 4.14. $C_{22}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 4.23%).

1-Phenyl-3-phenoxyethyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline (II).—A mixture of 1-phenyl-2-benzamido-3-phenoxypropane (2.5 g.), toluene (30 c.c.) and $POCl_3$ (7 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours. Toluene was distilled and the residue was poured into ice-water. The solution was washed with ether and

the acidic aqueous solution was cooled, basified, and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried. The residue obtained after removal of the solvent was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) as brownish plates, m.p. 75-76°. (Found : N, 4.48. $C_{22}H_{18}ON$ requires N, 4.47%).

1-Phenyl-3-hydroxymethylisoquinoline (III).—The above isoquinoline (II, 1 g.) was dehydrogenated by heating at 240-50° for 3 hours in CO_2 -atmosphere in presence of Pd-C (10%, 0.25 g.) and tetralin (10 c.c.). After removal of the catalyst the base was extracted with HCl. The acid solution was basified to yield the aromatised isoquinoline as a brownish viscous liquid (0.7 g.), which was characterised as *chloroplatinate*, m.p. 204-206° (decomp.). [Found : N, 3.08 ; Pt, 19.54. $2(C_{22}H_{17}ON).H_2PtCl_6$ requires N, 2.71 ; Pt, 18.9%].

The aromatised isoquinoline (1 g.) was refluxed for 8 hours with constant boiling hydrobromic acid (48%, 20 c.c.). The acid was distilled, the residue was poured in ice, and the solution was washed with ether. The aqueous solution was filtered, basified with ammonia, extracted with ether, and the ether removed after drying over sodium sulphate. The viscous liquid (0.9 g.) obtained solidified on chilling and scratching. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in light cream-coloured plates, m.p. 84-86°. (Found : N, 5.75. $C_{18}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 5.96%).

3-Piperidinocarbonylisoquinoline (IV).—A mixture of ethyl isoquinoline-3-carboxylate (Clemons and Hoggarth, *loc. cit.*) (5.5 g.), piperidine (6 c.c.) and diphenyl oxide (50 c.c.) was refluxed for 10 hours, cooled, and then extracted with HCl (dil.). The acid solution was basified with ammonia and extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was repeatedly washed with water, dried, and distilled to remove the solvent. The residue was distilled when a pale yellow liquid (7 g.), b.p. 210-15° 3-4 mm., was obtained. On chilling it solidified. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless plates, m.p. 94-95°. (Found : N, 11.98. $C_{15}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 11.67%).

The *picrate* crystallised from ethanol in yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 174-75°. (Found : N, 14.96. $C_{15}H_{16}ON_2.C_8H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 14.93%).

3-Piperidinomethylisoquinoline (V).—To a well-stirred suspension of $LiAlH_4$ (1 g.) in dry ether (250 c.c.) a solution of (IV, 4.5 g.) in dry ether (300 c.c.) was added dropwise at such a rate that the mixture refluxed, when a faint curdy white precipitate separated. The mixture was refluxed for 8 hours, poured in ice, and an aqueous solution of sodium potassium tartrate (20 g.) was added. The ether layer was separated and the aqueous solution extracted with ether. The combined ether solution was shaken with HCl (dil.), basified with ammonia, and then extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the ether left a viscous oil (1.5 g.).

The *picrate* crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 174-76°. (Found : C, 47.64 ; H, 3.29 ; N, 16.23. $C_{15}H_{16}N_2.2 C_8H_3O_7N_3$ requires C, 47.36 ; H, 3.51 ; N, 16.37%).

The *chloroplatinate* was obtained as a brown microcrystalline solid, m.p. 242° (decomp.).

3,4-Dihydro-3-benzylisoquinoline (VI).—A mixture of P_2O_5 (300 g.) and H_3PO_4 (89%, 192 g.) was heated at 100° under stirring in an oil bath for an hour. *N*-Formyl- α -benzyl- β -phenylethylamine (70 g.) was added at room temperature, followed by addition of $POCl_3$ (60 c.c.). The mixture was cautiously heated at 100° with vigorous stirring, when there was much foaming. The temperature was raised to 110° during 3 hours and then kept at 125-30° for 3½ hours. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into ice, and the solution was washed with benzene. The aqueous solution was basified with NaOH and thoroughly extracted with benzene. After removal of the benzene the residue was distilled to yield the base (50 g.), b.p. 178-82°/1 mm.

The *picrate* crystallised from ethanol in yellow plates, m.p. 262-63°. (Found: N, 12.32. $C_{16}H_{15}N.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 12.44%).

3-*Benzylisoquinoline* (VII).—A mixture of (VI, 40 g.), Pd-C (10%, 10 g.) and tetralin (350 c.c.) was heated under a current of CO_2 in an oil bath at 240-50° for 5 hours. The mixture was cooled, filtered, and the residue was washed with benzene. The washings and the filtrate were combined and thoroughly extracted with cold HCl (dil.). The acid solution was washed with ether, basified with NaOH, and the separated oil was extracted with benzene. The benzene solution was dried (K_2CO_3) and distilled to remove benzene. The residue was distilled to yield an almost colorless oil (32 g.), b.p. 188-92°/1 mm. (Found: N, 6.22. $C_{16}H_{13}N$ requires N, 6.39%). Rügheimer (*loc. cit.*) recorded b.p. 311°/23 mm and m.p. 104°.

The *picrate* crystallised from ethanol in yellow cottony needles m.p. 181-82°. (Found: N, 12.32. $C_{16}H_{13}N.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 12.5%). Rügheimer (*loc. cit.*) recorded m.p. 199°.

The *hydrochloride* was crystallised from absolute ethanol in colorless plates. It does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 5.22. $C_{16}H_{13}N.HCl$ requires N, 5.48%).

3-(α -1-Piperidinobenzyl)-isoquinoline (VIII)

(a). 3-(α -Bromobenzyl)-isoquinoline *Hydrobromide*.—To a solution of 3-benzylisoquinoline (12 g.) in CCl_4 (dry, 125 c.c.) benzoyl peroxide (0.05 g.) was added, followed by a solution of bromine (9 g.) in CCl_4 (dry, 25 c.c.) dropwise under cooling. At first bromine was decolorised very rapidly and gradually a yellowish crystalline precipitate began to form. On further addition of bromine the precipitate turned reddish brown and pasty in nature. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. CCl_4 was decanted and the residual pasty brownish solid triturated with acetic acid when it became granular in nature. It was filtered, washed with acetic acid, and finally with ether. The yellowish solid (9 g.) was used directly for the next operation.

(b). To the above compound (5 g.) piperidine (40 c.c.) was added under cooling. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hours. After removing piperidine by distillation under reduced pressure the residue was treated with water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was repeatedly washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the ether left a highly viscous base (5 g.).

The *picrate* crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 181-83°. (Found: N, 12.9. $C_{21}H_{22}N_2.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 13.2%).

The *phosphate* was recrystallised from methanol as a colorless, microcrystalline powder, m.p. 180-82°. (Found: N, 4.01; P, 17.4. $C_{21}H_{22}N_2.4H_3PO_4$ requires N, 4.03; P, 17.86%).

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